

CONSTRUCTION THEORY OF CRITICAL THINKING AS PROCESS TOWARDS REFRACTION THINKING IN MATHEMATICS

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ABSTRACT

Refraction is the event change or bending in direction wave as a result of pass through the boundary of two mediums that have different densities. Downey using a metaphor of light to describe the refraction the generated from reflection toward critical thinking. Refraction occurs because of the reflection of "implied" by the light passing through a medium that lead to critical thinking, so that the light emitted from medium is not the same such as reflection. This means, the components which passed of refraction thinking is reflection and critical thinking. This study discusses the construction of critical thinking as a process towards refraction thinking based on the notion and reasoning of critical thinking in mathematics.

Keyword: Critical Thinking, Refraction Thinking

INTRODUCTION

Refraction is the event change or bending in direction wave as a result of pass through the boundary of two mediums that have different densities. Light as waves undergo refraction when passing through the boundary of two mediums for instance when light comes from air into water it will be deflected beam direction.

In the health field, refraction occurs at the sight. Vision occurs because the eyes have to focus incoming light on the retina, which means to bend light as it enters the eye. Structures that perform refractive eye is the cornea and lens.

Downey (2005) used the *metaphor* to describe the refraction of light resulting from reflection toward critical thinking (Figure 1). Refraction is a process in which light (reflection) hit a medium that causes a "reaction" to the medium that trigger critical thinking. According to Pagano and Roselle (2009), refraction occurs due to the reflection of the "implied" by the light passing through a medium that lead to critical thinking, so that the light emitted from the medium is not the same as reflection. This means, the components through which the thinking refraction is thinking reflection and critical thinking.

Figure 1. Process of the refraction

CRITICAL THINKING AS A PROCESS TO REFRACTION THINKING

Pagano and Roselle (2009) states that after the reflective thinking, the next process towards a more active mental process called critical thinking. Critical Thinking in one of the main objectives is to identify linkages different views therefore one needs to consider the collected materials and supplies taken in the reflection stage. In critical thinking, students are actively trying to develop the skills to conceptualize, analysis, synthesis, evaluation, remember, and apply information or to reach a conclusion or answer questions (Facione, 2013; Jenicek, 2011).

During the stage of critical thinking students learn how different situations that

absorb different systems to make connections and see the connection. About critical thinking, various definitions put forward by experts, but the critical thinking component suggested by experts contains a lot of similarities.

A person can be said to thinking critically when it has two aspects, namely: *cognitive skills* and intellectual ability to use those skills as a guide in acting. Facione (2013) defines critical thinking as a skill decide (judgment) by giving reasoned consideration to evidence, context, methods and concepts. It could be argued that critical thinking is thinking that aims to form a decision, for example, someone making a decision about what he believed or did (Bailin, 1999). Meanwhile, according Schafersman (1991), defines critical thinking is thinking with the right to obtain relevant and reliable knowledge. Critical thinking is logical thinking, reflective, responsible, and skillful thinking. From this definition a person who thinks critically can determine relevant information and can make the appropriate conclusions.

Relating to critical thinking, Lai (2011) describes critical thinking is a skill that consists of analyzing arguments, making inferences using inductive or deductive, assess or evaluate and make decisions. Critical thinking is also the ability to read with understanding and identifying the necessary materials. In addition it is also the ability to draw conclusions from a given set of data. Neither view of critical thinking by Pagano and Roselle (2009) which states that critical thinking is a process of thinking actively to develop skills in conceptualizing, analysis, synthesis, evaluation, and apply the information to reach a conclusion or answer.

Characteristics of critical thinking is creative, logical and rational, cautious and seek information, in accordance with a systematic and intellectual. Therefore, a person who would ask a question of critical thinking among other things as follows: (1) what can I take for granted; (2) whether I've 'explored' all views; (3) if I understand the

question; (4) what information I require the late (Osman, 2005).

Critical thinking can be identified through *self-reflection* by combining *systems*, meta-cognition and cognitive systems (Marzano, 2001). *Self system* involves the interaction of one's attitude, beliefs emotion, and motivation. Cognitive system consists of the evaluation, the setting in thinking, clarity and accuracy. While cognitive consisted of the utilization of knowledge, analysis (extending existing knowledge, produce new conclusions), comprehension (organizing material for long-term memory) and *retrieval* (recall). Meanwhile, according to Taylor (1992), critical thinking is the result of reflection to develop awareness in the minds and actions reflect.

Neither view Choy Chee S. (2012) who explains that the reflection part of the process of critical thinking specifically refers to the process of analyzing and making judgments about what has happened. Pressure said "make judgments" are revealed in the definition of Choy Chee (2012) explicitly states that the decision is part of critical thinking.

When referring to *the metaphor of light*, critical thinking is the stage at which the light hit the medium which affects in some way, thus causing the reaction medium. The main objective is to identify the relationship of critical thinking to a different view, it is therefore necessary to consider the information collected in the reflection stage. Thus in this study is a critical thinking process of selecting and linking alternatives that obtained at the time of reflection so that it can be taken into consideration to provide an answer.

CRITICAL THINKING AS A COMPONENT BUILD PROCESS REFRACTION THINKING

Critical thinking is the result of reflection and develop awareness reflect a person's thoughts, feelings and actions (Taylor, 1992; Dewey, 1933; Park Ji Yong, 2011). Reflective thinking is part of the

critical thinking process that specifically leads to the process of analyzing and making judgments about what has happened. Colley & Billics (2012) explains that reflective thinking is the key to critical thinking, reflective analysis which showed that students begin to critical thinking involves three taxonomic knowledge of both process and outcomes and generate new conclusions.

Relating to critical thinking, Lai (2011) explains that critical thinking skills include, among others: analyzing arguments, making inferences using inductive or deductive, assess or evaluate, and make decisions or solve problems. Students' ability to form and use critical thinking to solve problems is very important to use in everyday life (Win, 2004) given the ability to critical thinking is an important component in continuing education (Dawe, et al. 2005; Schon, 1987; Mezirow, 1990; Tiley & Marsh, 2009).

Plymouth University (2010) provide an indicator of the components of critical thinking. The indicator on the critical thinking component are as follows: 1) *Description*; clearly defines the information that will be completed, 2) *analysis*; examine and explain the parts of the appropriate information, providing a logical reason (*reasonable*), comparing and contrasting information to demonstrate understanding of the relationship, 3) *Evaluation*; assess the success or failure of something.

In his view, Facione (2013) describes critical thinking skills and dispositions consisting of (a habit). Critical thinking skills consist of: 1) *interpretation* is the ability to understand and express the meaning of the experience, data or events; 2) *analysis* is the ability to identify the relationship between statements, questions and concepts; 3) *inference* is the ability to identify the information needed to determine an accurate conclusions or hypotheses of information; 4) *evaluation* is the ability to assess the credibility of statements or other representations and assess the logical strength of the relationship between the statement. While the

disposition has diversity as attitudes and habits of critical thinking, namely 5) *explanation*, explaining again that information is fully understood by others, and 6) *self-regulation*, self-awareness to monitor one's cognitive activities. Facione (2000) defines a disposition to think a person's motivation of self-consistent to act towards others. The indicators of the components of critical thinking (Facione, 2013) is described in Table 1.

Table 1. Indicators of critical thinking component (Facione, 2013)

<i>Interpretation</i> Relating to comprehend and express the meaning of the experience, data or events.
<i>Analysis</i> Identifying the relationship between statements, questions and concepts.
<i>Inference</i> The ability to recognize the elements of what is needed to determine an accurate conclusions or hypotheses of information.
<i>Evaluation</i> Assess the credibility of statements or other representations and assess the logical strength of the relationship between the statement
<i>Explanation</i> describes the information back so fully understood by others.
<i>Self Regulasi</i> , self-awareness to monitor one's cognitive activities.

Krulick & Rudnick (1995) mentions that include elements of critical thinking test, question, connect, evaluate all aspects of the mathematical problem. Included are collect, organize, remember, and analyze information. Critical thinking is also the ability to identify the materials needed, but it is also the ability to draw conclusions from a given set of data.

Emphasis on critical thinking is described also by Sriven (Jenicek, 2011) is an intellectual process that is active in conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and evaluating. The component is based on the results of experience, thought and consideration in determining action. Costa (1985) illustrates

that critical thinking is a thought process that evaluates an expression, usually ending with the evaluation of decision making. Indicators of critical thinking component (Jenicek, 2011) are described in Table 2.

Table 2 Indicators of critical thinking component (Jenicek, 2011)

<i>Conceptualizing</i> Collect and organize information
<i>Applying</i> Using the information obtained for a variety of situations
<i>Analyzing</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify the parts of an information. Analyze the relationships between parts. Recognize information that is in principle
<i>Synthesizing</i> Integrate some of the information so as to form something new (hypothetical)
<i>Evaluating information</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide an assessment of an appropriate material intended purpose Concludes with a valid

To make the categories specified in advance some critical thinking component. Previously needs to be synchronized some existing components of critical thinking, which is a component of critical thinking Jenicek (2011) are abbreviated (KKJ); critical thinking Plymouth University (2010) are abbreviated (CTF) and critical thinking Facione (2013) are abbreviated (KKF). The critical thinking equality contained in Table 3.

Table 3 Critical thinking Jenicek Equality (2011), Plymouth University (2010), and Facione (2013)

Jenicek (2011)	Learning Development, Plymouth University (2010)	Facione (2013)
<i>Conceptualizing</i> Collect and organize information	<i>Description</i> Clearly defines the information that will be resolved	<i>Interpretation</i> Relating to comprehend and express the meaning of the experience, data or events.
<i>Applying</i> Using the information obtained for a variety of	<i>Analysis</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examine and explain the parts of the appropriate 	<i>Analysis</i> Identifying the relationship between statements, questions and

situations	information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> provide a reason (reasonable). Compare and contrast the different information Demonstrate an understanding of the relationship 	concepts..
<i>Analyzing</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify the parts of an information. Analyze the relationships between parts. Recognize information that is in principle 		
<i>Synthesizing</i> Integrate some of the information so as to form something new (hypothetical)		<i>Inference</i> The ability to identify the information needed to determine an accurate conclusions or hypotheses of information.
<i>Evaluating information</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide an assessment of an appropriate material intended purpose Concludes with a valid 	<i>Evaluation</i> Assess the success or failure of something	<i>Evaluation</i> Assess the credibility of statements or other representations and assess the logical strength of the relationship between the statement.
		<i>Explanation</i> Explaining back so that the information is fully understood by others..
		<i>Self Regulation</i> , self-awareness to monitor one's cognitive activities

In the comparison table above seem critical thinking component Jenicek (KKJ); critical thinking Plymouth University (CTF) and critical thinking Facione (KKF) as follows:

1. *Conceptualizing* components in *KKJ*, *Description* on CTF, and *Interpretation* at the KKF can be aligned for collecting and organizing information to make a concept related to understanding the problem
2. *Analysis* Component on the CTF is a combination of *Analysis* and *Inference* on KKJ. *Analysis* and *Inference* on KKJ can be compared with *Applying*, *Analyzing*, *Synthesizing* the KKF, as indicators of the components seen in the

components such as identifying relationships between concepts, and the ability to identify the elements necessary to make a conclusion.

3. *Evaluation* components can be aligned as it has similarities indicators, such as assessing the credibility of the conclusions logically.

Based on the similarity indicator on each component, it can be constructed component of critical thinking. The results of the construction of critical thinking shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Results of the construction of critical thinking

Jeniecek (2011)	Plymouth University (2010)	Facione (2013)	Critical thinking
<i>Conceptualizing</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Exploration the information</i>
<i>Applying</i>	<i>Analysis</i>	<i>Analysis</i>	<i>Relevance of informatioan</i>
<i>Analyzing</i>		<i>Inference</i>	
<i>Synthesizing</i>	<i>Evaluation</i>	<i>Evaluation</i>	<i>Evaluation</i>
<i>Evaluating information</i>		<i>Explanation</i>	
		<i>Self Regulation</i>	<i>clarification</i>

Based on the above table, the critical thinking acquired construction for the following reasons:

1. *Conceptualizing* components in *KKJ*, *Description* on *CTF*, and *Interpretation* at the *KKF* in general has an indicator organize information to make a concept related to understanding and defining it. A person should be able to explore the information to construct meaning / significance of the information, so that these components can be referred to *the exploration information*.
2. Because the components of *Applying*, *Analyzing*, *Synthesizing* in *KKJ*, and *Analysis*, *Inference* on *KKF* has an indicator that looks similar to the *analysis* in the *CTF* as identifying relationships between concepts, and the ability to identify the elements necessary to make a conclusion. This indicator is associated with each connecting information to make a

conclusion so called *Relevance of information*.

3. *Evaluation* component has similarity indicators on critical thinking component *KKJ*, *CTF* and *KKF* is like judging a valid conclusion.
4. Component of *clarification* is a combination of *explanation* component and *self-regulation* in the *KKF* because *explanation* and *self-regulation* is a disposition / critical thinking habits of a person, so that the component is only used to clarify the results obtained.

Components can be swapped positions reflective thinking towards critical thinking, the situation is likely to occur as follows:

1. When someone wants to collect and classify information identifying the first person to issue and interpret information. This process is a component description and define problems in reflective thinking that led to the exploration of information on critical thinking. Condition can be described as follows.

2. When someone asks you a few alternatives obtained from the identification of the problem is done correctly, then the process will lead to the process of comparing or linking information. This process is a component define the problem and Collection reflective thinking to the relevance of information on critical thinking. Condition can be described as follows.

3. When someone asks alternatives and perform testing of these alternatives, then chances are someone will clarify the alternatives are used. This process is a component conclusion and Collection belief of reflective thinking that led to clarification on critical thinking. This condition can be described as follows.

4. When someone asks you a few alternatives obtainable when identifying a problem, then the alternatives are evaluated correctness of such alternatives. This process is a component define the problem and Collection reflective thinking that led to the evaluation of critical thinking. Condition can be described as follows.

CONCLUSION

By the time given math problem, students will experience confusion sometimes allowing students to reflect. Students will tend to associate with the issue de knowledge. Subsequently, students evaluate the information collected at the time of reflection, so that will allow students to choose alternatives by eliminating information gradually. Then, students finish by considering some of the information so as to produce less information. Therefore, the process of thinking refraction is the thought process that "pursing" option from several alternatives by eliminating information gradually.

Critical thinking is very closely associated with the thinking of refraction. In everyday life, thinking refraction is always involved in the decision making. Taking decisions is sometimes easy, but it is more often difficult. The ease or difficulty making decisions depending on the number of available alternatives. The more alternatives available, it will be increasingly difficult for us to take a decision. Therefore, thinking refraction through a critical thinking is very important in solving the problem occurs on decision making

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